

2. Spiders collected from rice straw bundles placed in ricefields after harvest. IRRI, 1989.

also *Oxyopes* spp., *Tetragnatha* spp., *Argiope* sp., and *Dyschiriognatha* sp.

Plants and leafhoppers also were collected. It is important that several species of pests colonize the tents because they are needed as food for the beneficial species. □

M-phase in eggs of *Nephotettix virescens* (Distant)

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Growth and development of *N. virescens* from fertilized egg (zygote) to maturity depend largely on a coordinated sequence of increases in cell numbers, size, and differentiation. Somatic egg cells undergo cyclic events, such as interphase and M-phase (mitotic). The M-phase is a critical stage in embryonic development and an ideal stage for preventing rice pest development. It includes nuclear (karyokinesis) and cytoplasmic (cytokinesis) divisions. We characterized the M-phase in *N. virescens* eggs.

The insect was mass-reared on TN1 rice plants in the IRRI insectary. Eggs were collected daily from 1 to 8 d after oviposition and the onset of cleavage or nuclear division determined. (At $30 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$, *N.*

virescens eggs normally hatch 9 d after oviposition.)

Eggs were placed on a spot-plate with 2-3 drops of Ringer's solution and squashed with a glass rod for 1 min. Extracted chorions were fixed with Carnoy's solution (3 parts ethyl alcohol, 1 part glacial acetic acid) for 20 min.

One drop was placed on a fresh glass slide and air-dried for 15 min. A drop of 60% acetic acid was added to each slide and allowed to stand another 10-20 min. One drop of lacto-aceto-orcein was added and the mixture squashed with a bent needle.

1. Frequency of M-phase during nuclear division in *N. virescens* eggs at different days after oviposition. IRRI, 1989. n = 1,900 eggs.

Slides were viewed under oil immersion objective (1250x) of a binocular microscope fitted with a linear micrometer.

The M-phase of cleavage was monitored in 1,900 eggs. No nuclear division was found the first 4 d, when embryogenic cells were at the prophase stage. Onset of the M-phase was on day 5; it increased on day 6. Frequency of nuclear division peaked on day 7-8. A range of 13-37 dividing nuclei was observed during peak periods. It appears 6- to 8-d-old eggs (eyespot stage to dark egg stage) are ideal for observing nuclear division stages (Fig. 1, 2). □

2. Egg cells of *N. virescens* undergoing different stages of mitosis. a = interphase, b = prophase, c = prometaphase, d = metaphase. IRRI, 1989.

Weed management

Yield loss to weeds in upland rice at Parwanipur, Nepal

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We assessed yield loss due to weeds in dry seeded upland rice at Parwanipur in 1988.

Ghaiya 2 (MW10) was seeded 18 Jun at 20-cm spacing. The experimental field was fertilized with 60-30-30 kg NPK/ha. Half the N and all the P and K were applied basal; the remaining N was topdressed in two equal splits at 25 and 55 d after seeding.

Ten 5- × 3-m plots with different levels of weed infestation were established. Two samples of weeds within a 1-m² quadrat placed randomly in each plot were taken before maturity.

Weeds were identified, dried, and weighed. Rice yield from 5.6-m² areas was converted into g/m². A simple linear regression and correlation analysis was used to assess rice yield loss due to weed infestation.

Echinochloa colona, *E. crus-galli*, *Cyperus difformis*, *C. iria*, and *C. rotundus* were dominant.

The linear relationship ($r = 0.9602^{**}$) between dry weed weight and rice yield was negative and highly significant (see figure). The regression analysis $Y = 294.579 - 1.0568^{**} (\pm 0.3638) X$ estimated the reduction in

Relationship between weed dry weight and rice grain yield under upland condition. Parwanipur, India, 1988.

yield per unit increase in dry weed weight to be between 0.48% (1.4206 g/m²) and 0.23% (0.6929 g/m²), at 99% level of confidence.

The equation developed here could be used to assess yield loss caused by weeds in upland ricefields under conditions similar to those in Parwanipur. □

6% broadleaved weeds.

Of the herbicides and cultural treatments tested, thiobencarb at 1.5 kg ai/ha followed by one hand weeding at

25-30 d after sowing (DAS) gave the highest yield and net return (see table). Results with butachlor at the same rate and weeding schedule were similar. □

Weed control in direct sown rice cultivar (MW10) under rainfed upland conditions of Chhattisgarh, MP, India, 1984-86.^a

Treatment	Formulation	Rate applied (kg ai/ha)	Yield (t/ha)				Gross return (\$)	Cost of treatment (\$)	Net return (\$)
			1984	1985	1986	Mean			
Thiobencarb (saturn)	50 EC	2.0	3.5	1.2	0.8	1.8	185	25	160
Thiobencarb plus one hand weeding at 25-30 DAS	50 EC	1.5	3.7	2.8	2.2	2.9	288	35	253
Butachlor (Delchlor)	50 EC	2.0	2.9	1.0	1.0	1.6	164	26	138
Butachlor with one hand weeding at 25-30 DAS	50 EC	1.5	3.1	3.4	2.0	2.8	285	40	247
Butachlor (Machete)	50 EC	2.0	2.6	0.7	1.0	1.4	141	25	116
Butachlor with one hand weeding at 25-30 DAS	50 EC	1.5	2.7	2.8	2.0	2.5	251	40	211
Pendimethalin	30 EC	1.5	2.4	0.8	0.8	1.4	138	30	108
Hand weeding twice at 20 and 40 DAS			3.4	3.00	1.7	2.7	271	47	224
Weed-free check			3.2	3.1	2.4	2.9	290	67	223
Nonweeded control			1.3	0.8	0.4	0.8	83	00	83
Experiment mean			2.9	2.0	1.6	2.2			
LSD (0.05)			0.5	0.10	0.5				

^aRice \$100.00/t, thiobencarb \$6.00/liter, Delchlor \$6.34/liter, Machete \$6.34/liter, pendimethalin \$5.93, labor charges \$0.67/d, labor required for 2 weedings (40 + 30 DAS) and for weed-free check (40 + 30 + 20 + 10 DAS) in man-days/ha.

Water management

Weed control in direct seeded rice under upland conditions of Chhattisgarh, India

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We evaluated herbicides for effective and economical control of weeds in direct seeded rice under upland conditions. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with four replications. MW10 was the test variety.

The dominant weeds were *Echinochloa colona*, *Cyperus rotundus*, *Setaria glauca*, *Cynodon dactylon*, *Eclipta alba*, *Alternanthera* spp., and *Commelina* spp. The weed population included 65% grasses, 29% sedges, and

Effect of submergence depth on rice yield and water percolation and nitrogen leaching in sandy clay loam soils

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We measured the effect of different submergence depths on rice yield, water percolation, and nitrogen leaching in the sandy clay loam (Typic Haplustalf) soils of Thanjavur District. The experimental field had neutral soil reaction and low organic matter content (0.51%). Soil had 20% clay, 3% silt, 13% coarse sand, 63% fine sand with low CEC (9.7 meq/100 g) and exchangeable bases.

The experiment was repeated in two seasons--kharif (Jun-Oct) and rabi

(Oct-Jan)--for 3 yr (1985-87). Water depths were 2.5, 5.0, and 7.5 cm, maintained by irrigating the 6- × 5-m plots daily.

Loss of water to percolation was measured in 20-cm-diameter, 30-cm-high metal rings covered by polythene sheets. Percolation loss was measured daily from 8 d after planting to 15 d before harvest.

Leachate collected daily after basal and topdressed prilled urea was analyzed for ammoniacal N using magnesium oxide and for nitrate N using Devarda alloy. Nitrogen loss by leaching was quantified from N concentration in the leachate and amount of water lost by percolation.

Daily topping with 2.5 or 5.0 cm water significantly increased yield compared to 7.5 cm water depth during the dry season. Percolation loss increased with depth of submergence